

ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS. PART IV.
DETERMINATION OF THORIUM WITH 1-HYDROXY-2-NAPHTHOIC
ACIDS

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Thorium has been estimated by 1-hydroxy-, 1-hydroxy-4-bromo- and 1-hydroxy-4-nitro-2-naphthoic acids at p_H ranges from 3 to 5.2. Thorium may be separated from cerite earths and monazite sand. The common metals like Na, Ca, Sr, Mg, Zn, Ti, etc. do not interfere. Thorium could not be separated from zirconium with these acids.

In the previous part (Datta, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 257) it was shown that 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid and its bromo and nitro derivatives could be used for the quantitative determination of zirconium. These acids also afford a quantitative precipitation of thorium. Its estimation and separation from cerite earths and other metals have been described in the present paper. It is seen that of the three acids used, 1-hydroxy-4-bromo-2-naphthoic acid is the most effective precipitating agent for thorium; it produces quantitative precipitation at p_H range of 3.6 to 5.2, while the corresponding p_H ranges for the 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid and its nitro compound are 4.2 to 5.2 and 3.9 to 5.2 respectively. The sodium salt of the free acid may be more conveniently used than the free acid. Thorium may be separated from the cerite earths and from most of the common elements, excepting zirconium, which is precipitated almost within the same p_H range as thorium. Thorium may also be extracted from monazite sand with these reagents.

EXPERIMENTAL

The 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids were prepared and purified according to the methods described previously (Datta, *loc. cit.*). A stock solution of thorium nitrate (Merck's reagent quality) was prepared and its thorium content was determined by the standard oxalate method. The stock solutions of other metals were prepared either from their chlorides or nitrates (all reagent grades) and their metal contents determined by standard methods.

Procedure.—To an aliquot amount of thorium solution, made neutral to Congo red and heated below its boiling temperature, was added a hot 0.5% solution of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid. In the case of its sodium salt and the bromo and the nitro compounds, 1% solution in water (hot) was used. No precipitation appeared immediately, but on adding about 1 c.c. of 2% ammonium acetate solution, precipitate came down in all cases. The solution was further heated over the free flame for 2 minutes, but was not boiled, so that the precipitate became coarser and settled at the bottom of the beaker. The colour of the precipitates with 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid and its bromo and nitro compounds was white, orange and yellow respectively. The precipitates were filtered, washed with hot water several times and

then dried at 100° and ignited to the oxide to a constant weight. The results have been tabulated below. It is evident from Table I that up to 0.0071 g. of thorium may be estimated from 50 c.c. solution by the sodium salt of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid, but with bromo and nitro compounds, up to 0.0036 g. of thorium may be determined with nearest accuracy.

TABLE I

Estimation of thorium with 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids.

Thorium soln. = 50 c.c.

[·N indicates -2-naphthoic acid]

No.	ThO ₂ taken.	ThO ₂ found by			
		1-OH·N.	1-OH·N. (Na-salt)	1-OH-4-Br·N.	1-OH-4-NO ₂ ·N.
1.	0.0426 g.	0.0423 g.	0.0424 g.	0.0426 g.	0.0426 g.
2.	0.0284	0.0281	0.0282	0.0283	0.0282
3.	0.0035	0.0024	0.0026	0.0032	0.0031
4.	0.0018	...	...	0.0013	0.0011

Influence of p_n on the Precipitation of Thorium.—Buffer solutions in the p_n range of 2 to 6 were prepared according to standard directions. The procedure was to place 25 c.c. of the thorium nitrate solution, 50 c.c. of the buffer solution and 25 c.c. of the reagent solution in a 250 c.c. beaker and to heat the mixture below its boiling temperature with the subsequent addition of 1 c.c. of 2% ammonium acetate solution. The resulting precipitate was converted into the oxide in the usual manner. In all cases, a three to four fold excess of the reagent was added. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

ThO₂ taken = 0.0178 g.

Reagents.	ThO ₂ found at p_n			
	3.9	4.2	4.7	5.2
1-OH·N	0.0172 g.	0.0173 g.	0.0174 g.	0.0174 g.
1-OH·N (Na-salt)	0.0173	0.0175	0.0176	0.0176
1-OH-4-Br·N	0.0176	0.0178	0.0178	0.0177
1-OH-4-NO ₂ ·N	0.0174	0.0176	0.0177	0.0177

Separation of Thorium from the Cerite Earths.—Different amounts of standard cerium nitrate or lanthanum nitrate solutions were added to a definite quantity of thorium solution. The mixture was neutralised to Congo red and thorium was precipitated by all the reagents, as described before, and estimated as oxide. The results indicated in Table III show that thorium may be separated, with slight contamination, from solutions having thoria-earth oxide ratio up to 1:10 with the sodium salt of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid by single precipitation method, the corresponding ratios for bromo and nitro compounds are 1:16 and 1:14 respectively. The slight contamination, however, may easily be removed by double precipitation.

TABLE III

ThO₂ taken = 0.0142 g.

CeO ₂ added.	La ₂ O ₃ added.	Thoria: *RO.	ThO ₂ found.	CeO ₂ added.	La ₂ O ₃ added.	Thoria: *RO.	ThO ₂ found.	CeO ₂ added.	La ₂ O ₃ added.	Thoria: *RO.	ThO ₂ found.
With 1-OH-N (Na-salt).			With 1-OH-4-Br-N.			With 1-OH-4-NO ₂ -N.					
0.0276 g.	...	1:2	0.0143 g.	0.0552 g.	0.0304 g.	1:6	0.0144 g.	0.1104 g.	0.0304 g.	1:10	0.0145 g.
0.0276	0.0152 g.	1:3	0.0145	0.1104	0.0608	1:2	0.0145	0.1104	0.0712	1:14	0.0148
0.0552	0.0304	1:6	0.0146	0.1104	0.0912	1:14	0.0147	0.1104	0.1012	1:15	0.0151
0.0114	0.0304	1:10	0.0148	0.1104	0.1216	1:16	0.0148				

* RO stands for earth oxide.

Separation of Thorium from other metals.—Measured amounts of thorium nitrate solutions were added to definite quantities of metal salt solutions. The mixtures were brought to suitable p_H values by buffer solutions and the precipitation of thorium was carried out with these reagents as before. The precipitates were filtered, washed and ignited as usual. It is seen that Ca, Ba, Sr, Zn, Mg, Al, Cr, Mn and Ti do not cause any interference or coprecipitation. Metals like iron, cobalt and nickel are found to contaminate, though very slightly, the thorium precipitate; so double precipitation in those cases is necessary. Thorium cannot be separated from zirconium by these acids, as the latter is quantitatively precipitated almost within the same p_H range as the former. The results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

ThO ₂ taken.	Metal oxide added.	ThO ₂ found by		
		Na-salt of 1-OH-N.	1-OH-4-Br-N.	1-OH-4-NO ₂ -N.
0.0142 g.	BaO, 0.0250 g.	0.0142 g.	0.0143 g.	0.0143 g.
"	SiO, 0.0218	0.0140	0.0143	0.0142
"	CaO, 0.0316	0.0140	0.0144	0.0142
"	Al ₂ O ₃ , 0.0232	0.0143	0.0143	0.0144
"	*Fe ₂ O ₃ , 0.0181	0.0144	0.0144	0.0143
0.0284	Cr ₂ O ₃ , 0.0232	0.0285	0.0286	0.0285
"	MnO ₂ , 0.0105	0.0281	0.0282	0.0284
"	ZnO, 0.0153	0.0281	0.0282	0.0283
"	MgO, 0.0150	0.0282	0.0284	0.0285
"	TiO ₂ , 0.0252	0.0280	0.0282	0.0283
"	*CoO, 0.0167	0.0287	0.0286	0.0287
c "	*NiO, 0.0266	0.0286	0.0285	0.0287

* Indicates double precipitation.

Separation of Thorium from Uranium.—Thorium may also be separated from uranium to a great extent. Uranium is not precipitated with these reagents but a

slight quantity is held up by the thorium precipitate, when the latter is precipitated from mixtures having larger amounts of uranium. The separation limit for uranium has been determined, as uranium is found to occur along with thorium in nature. Thorium was therefore precipitated with these reagents from mixtures having different proportions of thorium and uranium by following the same procedure. The sodium salt of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid may separate thorium from solutions having thorium-uranium oxide ratio up to 1:6 by double precipitation method; the corresponding ratios for the bromo and nitro compounds are 1:15 and 1:20 respectively. The results are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

ThO ₂ taken	U ₃ O ₈ added.	ThO ₂ : U ₃ O ₈ .	ThO ₂ found by		
			1-OH-N (Na-salt).	1-OH-4-Br-N.	1-OH-4-NO ₂ -N.
0.0104 g.	0.0424 g.	1:4	0.0106 g.	0.0103 g.	0.0103 g.
"	0.0636	1:6	0.0106	0.0104	0.0106
"	0.1060	1:10	0.0112	0.0105	0.0106
0.0142	0.1696	1:12	..	0.0145	0.0146
"	0.2120	1:15	...	0.0147	0.0148
"	0.2756	1:19	...	0.0147	0.0150
"	0.2862	1:20	...	0.0148	...
"	0.3604	1:25	...	0.0151	...

Extraction of Thorium from Monazite Sand.—Acid extract of a sample of Travancore monazite sand was prepared according to the method of Raghava Rao *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 458). Thorium was estimated in this extract by single precipitation as before. Estimation with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid was also carried out side by side to compare the results, which are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Wt. of Monazite.	ThO ₂ obtained With Na-salt of 1-OH-N.		ThO ₂ obtained With 1-OH-4-Br-N.	
1. 1.3250 g.	0.0969 g.	7.32%	0.0970 g.	7.32%
2. 1.5031	0.1098	7.31	0.1120	7.32
3. 1.1232	0.0822	7.32	0.0821	7.31
	With 1-OH-4-NO ₂ -N.		With <i>m</i> -nitrobenzoic acid.	
1. 1.3250	0.0968	7.31	0.0967	7.30
2. 1.5031	0.1098	7.31	0.1097	7.30
3. 1.1232	0.0822	7.32	0.0821	7.31

Composition of Thorium Salt of 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid.—Thorium salts of these acids were prepared as usual. The salts were washed with hot alcohol several times in order to remove the free reagents, if any, and then washed with ether and dried at 100°-125°. Aliquot quantities were ignited to the oxide in a platinum crucible

and weighed to a constant weight. The results obtained suggest the following formula for the thorium salts of these acids.

The latter formula seems to be more probable for thorium; direct weighing method for the estimation of thorium, however, is not practicable.

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